

MARK TWAIN'S WRITING STYLE AND LANGUAGE IN
"THE ADVENTURES OF HUCKLEBERRY FINN"

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Abstract: This article deals with Mark Twain's writing style and language in his novel "The Adventures of Huckleberry Finn".

Keywords: scene, time, narrator, character, dialect, slavery, n-words, adventure novels, criticism

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola Mark Tvenning "Geklberri Finning sarguzashtlari" romanidagi uslubi va tiliga bag'ishlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: makon, zamon, hikoyachi, xarakter, sheva, qullik, n-so'zlar, sarguzasht romanlar, tanqid

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается стиль письма и язык Марка Твена в его романе «Приключения Гекльберри Финна».

Ключевые слова: сцена, время, рассказчик, персонаж, диалект, рабство, н-слова, приключенческие романы, критика.

"The Adventures of Huckleberry Finn" was first published on December 10, 1884 (UK and Canada), 1885 (United States) by Mark Twain. It consists of 43 chapters, 366 pages. The scene is along The Mississippi River, events take place in the 1830s or 1840s. The illustrations are done by E. W. Kemble and they are altogether one hundred and seventy-four illustrations. There are two brief statements to the reader that appear before Chapter 1; both of these display Twain's trademark sense of humor. In the first

statement, under the heading “Notice,” Twain warns readers against trying to find any kind of deep meaning in the book. He mentions different punishments for readers who search motive, moral, or plot within the narrative. The second statement, called “Explanatory,” informs readers that the dialects used by different characters in the book are based on real regional dialects, and have been researched thoroughly. As Twain notes, “I make this explanation for the reason that without it many readers would suppose that all these characters were trying to talk alike and not succeeding.”¹

The book was considered as one of the most important American works of fiction due to its artistry and evocation. The novel gained popularity because of its ability to have crucial lessons together with its entertaining features. The book tells the story of Huckleberry Finn, who was known in the author’s previous book -“The Adventures of Tom Sawyer” and a runaway slave called Jim and their adventures in the Mississippi River. The story is narrated by Huck Finn. Mark Twain also paints a rich portrait of the slave Jim, a character unequalled in American literature: he is guileless, rebellious, genuine, superstitious, warmhearted, ignorant, and astute all at the same time.

The book is a sequel to another of the author's successful adventure novels, “The Adventures of Tom Sawyer”, originally published in 1876. Although “The Adventures of Tom Sawyer” is very much a “boys' novel”—humorous, suspenseful, and intended purely as entertainment—“The Adventures of Huckleberry Finn” also mentions problematic topics of that time such as slavery, prejudice, hypocrisy, and morality.

The book confronted some controversies. It was criticized and even banned from libraries because of its vernacular language. However the work of fiction gained popularity. John H. Wallace says “The Adventures of Huckleberry Finn” by Mark Twain, is the most grotesque examples of racist trash ever written (Leonard,16). In his essay called «The case against Huck Finn» Wallace analyses racism in the work. He

¹ Twain, Mark. *The Adventures of Huckleberry Finn*. New York: Chatto & Windus/ Charles L. Webster, 1885. Print.

mentions that Mark Twain's writing style seemed to be offensive to African American leaders, especially the adolescents.

Jim's characterization is given negatively and that is the key reason for banning from libraries. Mark Twain portrays Jim as «subhuman; feeble-minded, wicked, and indolent, which shows that he is inferior to the white people».

Different dialects are used in this book including the Missouri negro dialect; the extremest form of the backwoods south-western dialect, the ordinary «pike-country» dialect; and four modified varieties of this last.

Together with the dialects, Mark Twain makes a use of grammatically incorrect structures. «She put me in them new clothes again, and I couldn't do nothing but sweat and sweat, and feel all cramped up» (chapter I, page 18) «I didn't care no more about him; because I don't take no stock in dead people» (chapter I, page 18). «They get down on a thing when they don't know nothing about it» (chapter I, page 19). In these sentences two negative forms are used.

Twain's intentional use of bad grammar gets much criticism. Actually, Twain tries to structure the sentences with grammar mistakes to represent the language spoken by rural populations in the pre-civil war south.

The word «nigger» is used 213 times in the book and it caused much criticism. It is argued that the frequent usage of n-words shows a racist content. During the times of slavery, the two races were very different and the whites were thought to be superior. Sharing of common things was unheard of. However, in the novel, Mark Twain points out that a person can share common interests with another person regardless of his or her racial background. "People would call me a low-down Abolitionist and despise me for keeping mum-but that don't make no difference. I ain't a-going to tell" (Twain, 50). These words were spoken by Huck. He was telling Jim that he won't tell anybody about his escape from slavery. If the novel were racist, Huck could not have even attempted to help his friend in escaping from slavery.

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